

CAPABILITY AND CONFIDENCE OF PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS IN INTEGRATING COMPREHENSIVE SEXUALITY EDUCATION: BASIS FOR TRAINING PLAN

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Capability and Confidence of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education: Basis for Training Plan

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the capability and confidence of private school teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education on identified learning areas utilized a standardized questionnaire based on Learning New, Learning Now, Learning Next: Orientation of Teachers on the Awareness on Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) was administered to 57 teachers from 6 private schools in the District of Hinigaran. Results revealed that most of the respondents are females, 30 years old and below, with bachelor's degree and with 10 years and below length of service and most are teaching science while only 2 respondents are teaching personality development subjects. As a whole the level of capability of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education is very high while in terms of learning areas handled, MAPEH, Science and Personal Development obtained very high while Araling Panlipunan and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao obtained high level. As a whole the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education is very high while in terms of learning areas handled, MAPEH, Science and Personal Development obtained very high while Araling Panlipunan and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao obtained high level. There is a significant relationship between the level of capability of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and the learning area handled. There is no significant relationship between the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and the learning area handled. There is a significant relationship between the level of capability of teachers and their level of confidence in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education.

Keywords: *capability, private school teachers, comprehensive, sexuality*

Introduction

The vision of the Department of Education states: "We dream of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. As a learner-centered public institution, the Department of Education continuously improves itself to better serve its stakeholders" (DepEd Order 36, s. 2013).

However, despite of the efforts of the Department of Education to provide and help the youth for a brighter future, recent reports stress the rising incidences of early pregnancy, sexual violence, and human-immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection among young Filipinos. The sexual morality of Filipino teenagers is in great decline based on the many cases of unwanted pregnancy, the spread of sexually transmitted diseases (STD), liberality in sexual behaviors, and many other evident consequences. This is a very important concern for many families, school administrators, church authorities, and other involved institutions. With this unfortunate situation, it is easier to judge how our teens have immersed themselves in the river of sexual immorality (Cordero, 2018).

Many low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) are integrating comprehensive sexuality education (CSE) into educational systems to promote youth and adolescents sexual and reproductive health and rights (ASRHR) as part of attempts to accelerate the attainment of universal health coverage and sustainable development goals by 2030.

Meeting ASRHR is crucial for creating healthy socio-economic environments and promoting wellbeing in adolescents and young adults. Yet achieving ASRHR presents major global challenges. For instance, deep-seated discomfort about adolescent sexuality persists because of social, cultural, religious, structural, and institutional factors. In many countries sexual abstinence is the dominant social message despite a body of evidence showing that abstinence education has limited or no effect on reducing risks. Additionally, in some societies premarital sex is taboo. Trainee teachers not exposed to CSE in their own upbringing can lack the knowledge and skills to deliver CSE (Chavula, Zulu, and Hurtig, 2022).

The CSE focuses on the integration of scientific, age- and developmentally appropriate, and culturally and gender-responsive information on the cognitive, emotional, physical, and social aspects of sexuality in the K-12 Curriculum (Malipot, 2021).

While there is extensive documentation on these challenges, there is a notable gap in understanding the capability and confidence of teachers in integrating CSE into educational systems.

These premises urge the researcher to conduct this study on the capability and confidence of private school teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) on identified learning areas. This study explores these dimensions as basis for a training plan.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the level of capability and confidence of private school teachers in integrating

Comprehensive Sexuality Education on identified learning areas. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex
 - 1.3. Educational attainment
 - 1.4. Length of Service
2. What percentage of private school teachers handle the following identified learning areas:
 - 2.1. Music, Arts, P.E. & Health
 - 2.2. Araling Panlipunan
 - 2.3. Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
 - 2.4. Science
 - 2.5. Personal Development
3. What is the level of capability of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of learning area handled?
4. What is the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of learning area handled?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of capability of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and the learning area handled?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and the learning area handled?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the level of capability and the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education?

Methodology

Research Design

This research aimed to determine the level of capability and level of confidence of private school teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) on identified learning areas of private school teachers in the District of Hinigaran for SY 2022-2023.

Descriptive-correlational method of research was used in this study in its attempt to determine the level of capability and confidence of private school teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education on identified learning areas. Research studies that seek to establish the relationship between various variables and present static images of situations employ descriptive correlational design (Descriptive Correlational Design Definition & Goals, 2023). A descriptive correlational research design describes the variables and measures the extent of the relationships that occur between and among the variables (Aprecia, Barrera, Cuares, et al., 2022). In this study, the level of capability and level of confidence of private school teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education on identified learning areas and their relationship were assessed.

Respondents

The total population of 57 private school teachers from the Municipality of Hinigaran were included as respondents of the study. Thus, the sample size was not computed. Total population sampling includes all individuals within the population of interest, allowing for in-depth insights into the phenomenon being studied. This comprehensive approach minimizes the risk of overlooking important insights from members who might otherwise be excluded. Table 1 below shows the number of private school teachers by school.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents per School*

<i>School</i>	<i>Population</i>
A	7
B	10
C	7
D	17
E	14
F	2
Total	57

Instrument

This study utilized a standardized questionnaire based on Learning New, Learning Now, Learning Next: Orientation of Teachers on the Awareness on Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE). An orientation module Prepared by Center for Health Solutions and Innovations Philippines, Inc. (CHSI) with the support from United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) and the Department of Education (DepEd).

The questionnaire is composed of three (3) parts. Part 1 is to assess the demographic profile of the respondents as to age, sex, highest educational attainment, years in service, and learning areas handled.

Part 2 of the questionnaire is to assess the level of capability of teachers in integrating comprehensive sexuality education with 13 items, and part 3 is to measure the level confidence of teachers in integrating CSE with 17 items.

Procedure

To gather data, the researcher first sought approval from the principals of private schools in the Municipality of Hinigaran. After being approved, she then asked permission from the respondents to conduct the survey.

After approval was obtained, the researcher distributed the survey forms to the teachers. After giving them ample time to answer the survey forms, the researcher then collected, tallied, and tabulated the data.

Data Analysis

The data obtained in this study were subjected to appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical procedures. In the analyses and interpretation of data, different statistical tools were used:

To answer the statement of problem no.1, what is the profile of teachers in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, frequency, and percent distribution were used.

To answer the statement of problem no. 2, what percentage of private school teachers handle the following identified learning areas: Music, Arts, P.E. & Health, Araling Panlipunan, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, Science, and Personal Development, frequency and percent distribution were used.

To answer the statement of problem no. 3, what is the level of capability of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of the learning area handled, mean was used.

To answer the statement of problem no. 4 which states, what is the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of the learning area handled, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problems no. 5 and 6, which states, is there a significant relationship between the level of capability and confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and the learning area handled, Chi-square was used.

To answer statement of the problem no.7 which states, is there a significant relationship between the level of capability and the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education, Chi-square was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered from this study.

Profile of Teachers

The table below reveals the profile of private school teachers in the District of Hinigaran.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Profile of Private School Teachers in the District of Hinigaran*

Variable	Categories	(f)	(%)
Sex	Male	17	29.80
	Female	40	70.20
	Total	57	100.00
Age	30 years old and below	35	61.40
	31-40 years old	9	15.80
	41-50 years old	6	10.50
	51-60 years old	7	12.30
	Total	57	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor	51	89.50
	Masters	6	10.50
	Total	57	100.00
Length of Service	10 years and below	48	84.20
	11-20 years	6	10.50
	21-30 years	3	5.30
	Total	57	100.00

Based on the table above, in terms of sex, 17 or 29.80 percent are males while 40 or 70.20 percent are females. In terms of age, 35 are 30 years old and below, nine (9) are 31-40 years old, six (6) are 41-50 years old, and 51-60 years old. In terms of highest educational

attainment, 51 are bachelor’s degree holders and 6 are master’s degree holders.

In terms of length of service, 48 have 10 years and below length of service, six (6) are 11-20 years in service, and 3 are 21-30 years in service.

In general, most of the respondents are females, mostly are 30 years old and below, bachelor’s degree holders, and with 10 years and below length of service.

Identified Learning Areas

The table below presents the percentage of private school teachers in the Municipality of Hinigaran handling the identified learning areas.

Table 2. Frequency and Percent Distribution of Private School Teachers in the Municipality of Hinigaran Handling the Identified Learning Areas

<i>Identified Learning Areas</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
MAPEH	13	22.80
Araling Panlipunan	12	21.10
Edukasyon sa Pagpakatao	10	17.50
Science	20	35.10
Personal Development	2	3.50
Total	57	100.00

The table above reveals that 13 or 22.80 percent of the respondents are handling MAPEH, 12 or 21.10 percent are handling Araling Panlipunan, 10 or 17.50 percent are handling Edukasyon sa Pagpakatao, 20 or 35.10 percent are handling science, and two (2) are handling Personal Development. This implies that a little number of the respondents are handling Personal Development while most of the respondents are handling science.

Level of Capability of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education

The table presents the level of capability of teachers in integrating comprehensive sexuality education in terms of learning areas handled and when taken as a whole.

Table 3. Level of Capability of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of Learning Area Handled

<i>Learning Area Handled</i>	<i>Level of Capability</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
MAPEH	Very High	7	4.30	Very High
	High	6		
	Moderate	0		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	0		
Araling Panlipunan	Very High	6	3.89	High
	High	2		
	Moderate	4		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	0		
Edukasyon Sa Pagpakatao	Very High	5	3.99	High
	High	3		
	Moderate	1		
	Low	1		
	Very Low	0		
Science	Very High	16	4.40	Very High
	High	4		
	Moderate	0		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	0		
Personal Development	Very High	2	4.81	Very High
	High	0		
	Moderate	0		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	0		
Total		57	4.21	Very High

Based on the table , in terms of teachers handling MAPEH, seven (7) got very high level and six (6) got high level of capability in integrating comprehensive sexuality education with an overall mean of 4.30 interpreted as very high.

In terms of teachers handling Araling Panlipunan, six (6) have high level, two (2) have high, and four (4) have moderate level of capability in integrating comprehensive sexuality education with an overall mean of 3.89 interpreted as high.

In terms of teachers handling Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, five (5) got very high, three (3) got high, one (1) got moderate, and one (1) got low level of capability in integrating comprehensive sexuality education with an overall mean of 3.99 interpreted as high.

In terms of teachers handling Science, 16 obtained very high level, and four (4) got high level of capability in integrating comprehensive sexuality education with an overall mean of 4.40 interpreted as very high.

In terms of teachers handling Personal Development, two (2) obtained very high level of capability in integrating comprehensive sexuality education with an overall mean of 4.81 interpreted as very high. With a total of 57 teachers, as a whole 4.21 was the obtained mean interpreted as very high.

This implies that teachers are capable in integrating comprehensive sexuality education. This means that they can identify key content standards of Comprehensive Sexuality Education in the curriculum guide, create age- appropriate activities on CSE, integrate CSE content standards in my learning area with other learning areas, talk to students about sexuality and reproductive health, name the reproductive health organs in front of my class, and explain puberty and all the changes that happen to the minds and bodies of young people during this period.

The result is not congruent to the statement of Shibuya, Estrada, Sari, et al., (2023), some of the teachers were hesitant to talk to students at school about sexual and reproductive health (SRH). This is because SRH is still a sensitive topic, and it might be necessary to show what the right way is as an option for students. It seems difficult to facilitate interest in CSE among teachers. The teacher is afraid that sex education will promote ‘sexual awakening’ among children and may encourage student sexual behavior. Moreover, some of the parents have not yet acknowledged talking about sexuality at school, because they felt that sex education fosters ‘sexual awakening’ among children. The teacher also expressed concerns on losing their moral authority as a professional educator in front of students, which results in a loss of control over students. Furthermore, the relationship between students and educators is not easy to develop since teachers are perceived as disciplinarians.

The challenge of implementation in school is that majority of the official subjects on traditional sex education have not been integrated into the official curriculum. In addition, some teachers are afraid that students tended to easily learn about sex recently; thus, there is a gap between teachers and students. Furthermore, the parents complained to the school principal, because a teacher provided a sexual topic (as a CSE curriculum) to students at school. Regarding consideration of minorities, three main points were identified: intellectually disabled learners; HIV-positive adolescents; and homosexuals (Shibuya, Estrada, Sari, et al., 2023).

Level of Confidence of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education

The table reveals the level of confidence of teachers in integrating comprehensive sexuality education when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of learning areas handled.

Table 4. Level of Confidence of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education When Taken as a whole and when grouped in Terms of Learning Area Handled

<i>Learning Area Handled</i>	<i>Level of Confidence</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
MAPEH	Very High	9	4.39	Very High
	High	4		
	Moderate	0		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	0		
Araling Panlipunan	Very High	5	3.74	High
	High	3		
	Moderate	3		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	1		
Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao	Very High	4	3.72	High
	High	3		
	Moderate	1		
	Low	2		
	Very Low	0		
Science	Very High	16	4.56	Very High
	High	4		

	Moderate	0		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	0		
Personal Development	Very High	2	4.94	Very High
	High	0		
	Moderate	0		
	Low	0		
	Very Low	0		
	Total	57	4.21	Very High

Based on the table, in terms of level confidence in integrating comprehensive sexuality education, nine (9) teachers handling MAPEH obtained a very high level and four (4) obtained high level of confidence with an overall mean of 4.39, interpreted as very high.

In terms of teachers handling Araling Panlipunan, five (5) have very high, three (3) have high, and three (3) have moderate level of confidence in integrating CSE with an overall mean of 3.74 interpreted as high.

In terms of teachers handling Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, four (4) teachers got very high level, three (3) got high, one (1) got moderate, and two (2) got low level of confidence with an overall mean of 3.72 interpreted as high.

In terms of teachers handling Science, 16 have very high and four (4) have high level of confidence with an overall mean of 4.56 interpreted as very high.

In terms of teachers handling Personal Development, two (2) obtained very high level of confidence in integrating CSE with an overall mean of 4.94 interpreted as very high.

As a whole, in terms of confidence in integrating comprehensive sexuality education, the teachers obtained a very high level with a mean of 4.21. It can be implied that teachers teaching Science, MAPEH and Personal development learning areas are more confident compared to teachers handling Araling Panlipunan and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao. This can be possible because Science, MAPEH and Personal development learning areas have topics related to CSE like MAPEH where teachers are tackling topics about health, science where teachers discuss about the different parts and systems of the body and personal development subjects that encompasses a broad spectrum of areas to enhance an individual's life, skills, and self-awareness.

To support the findings, according to Venketsamy and Kinear (2020), although it was possible to include the CSE content in life skills as well as in other subjects, the participatory teaching methods required might challenge teachers not trained in those methodologies. Teachers agreed with the problems relating to 'time in classroom for teaching', 'giving learning enough time', and 'knowing the right methods to use so we do not affect negatively on what learners need to know when they so young' and emphasized that 'our attitudes need to be positive.

Furthermore, all the participants raised the issues of the provision of resources as a limitation to teaching new content, which is a direct contradiction of the Department of Education's (2001) argument that sexuality education is cost-effective and builds on existing resources (teachers and curricula) and requires only low-cost investment on the part of donors and programmes. Teachers specifically remarked on how the paucity of resources, such as just the usual teaching and learning support materials (LTSM), was a constraint in the classroom, and the lack of resources as a challenge to the support she could offer life skills teachers who already have to teach everything with nothing (Venketsamy and Kinear, 2020).

Relationship between Level of Capability of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and Learning Area Handled

The table below reveals the relationship between the level of capability of private school teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and learning area handled.

Table 5. Relationship between Level of Capability of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and Learning Area Handled

Learning Area Handled	Level of Capability					Total
	Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Very Low	
MAPEH	7	6	0	0	0	13
Araling Panlipunan	6	2	4	0	0	12
Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao	5	3	1	1	0	10
Science	16	4	0	0	0	20
Personal Development	2	0	0	0	0	2
Total	36	15	5	1	0	57

Computed Value (x2)= 21.399
 P-value= 0.045
 Decision= Reject Ho
 Interpretation= Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the table above, most of the respondents obtained very high level of capability with 36 out of 57 total respondents where seven (7) are handling MAPEH, six (6) are handling Araling Panlipunan, 5 are handling Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, 16 are handling Science, and two (2) are handling Personal Development.

Using the Chi square test of independence at 0.05 level of significance, a computed (χ^2) value of 21.39 was obtained which is above the p-value of 0.045. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the level of capability of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and the learning area handled. This means that integrating CSE is influenced by the learning area handled by teachers. It shows that teachers handling Science and Personal Development learning areas have very high capability in integrating CSE. While other teachers teaching Araling Panlipunan may still have very high capability, but also registered high and moderate capabilities, as it is not their specialization and expertise based on the learning areas they handle.

The result is supported by Chavula, Zulu, & Hurtig, (2022) stating that social, economic, cultural, political, legal, and financial contextual factors influence the implementation and integration of CSE into national curricula and educational systems. Stakeholder collaboration and involvement in the design and appropriateness of interventions is critical. Reported aspects of the interventions include core CSE content, delivery methods, training materials and resources, and various teacher-training factors. Reasons for adoption include perceived benefits of CSE, experiences and characteristics of both teachers and learners, and religious, social and cultural factors. Broad system characteristics include strengthening links between schools and health facilities, school and community-based collaboration, coordination of CSE implementation, and the monitoring and evaluation of CSE. Ultimately, the availability of resources, national policies and laws, international agendas, and political commitment will impact upon the extent and level of integration.

Relationship between Level of Confidence of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and Learning Area Handled

The table reveals the relationship between the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and learning area handled.

Table 6. Relationship between Level of Confidence of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and Learning Area Handled

Learning Area Handled	Level of Confidence					Total
	Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Very Low	
MAPEH	9	4	0	0	0	13
Araling Panlipunan	5	3	3	0	1	12
Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao	4	3	1	2	0	10
Science	16	4	0	0	0	20
Personal Development	2	0	0	0	0	2
Total	36	14	4	2	1	57

Computed Value (χ^2)= 25.38
 p-value= 0.063
 Decision= No sufficient evidence to reject Ho
 Interpretation= Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the table above, most of the teachers obtained very high level of confidence in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education with 36 out of 57 total respondents where nine (9) are handling MAPEH, 5 are handling Araling Panlipunana, four (4) are handling Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, 16 are handling Science, and two (2) are handling Personal Development learning area.

Using the Chi square test of independence at 0.05 level of significance, a computed (χ^2) value of 25.38 was obtained which is above the p-value of 0.063. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the level of confidence of teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education and the learning area handled. This means that the confidence of teachers in integrating CSE is not influenced by the learning area handled by teachers. This can happen because subjects like Science and MAPEH have topics relevant to CSE unlike subject like Araling Panlipunan and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao which most topics covered are not relevant to CSE content and that teachers handling these subjects are not that confident compared to teachers handling science and MAPEH.

The result is supported by Fisher and Cummings (2016) cited by Brodeur, Fernet, & Hébert, (2023), where in their study, participants were asked to respond to questions addressing their confidence in teaching sexuality education topics, ability to plan and implement sexuality lessons with the National Health Education Standards, and ability/proficiency in the National Teacher Preparation Standards for Sexuality Education. The topic of identity (36%), which addresses people’s understanding of who they are, was the only topic identified by the National Sexuality Education Standards that teachers were uncomfortable teaching. The majority of the educators felt very confident in their abilities to teach lessons integrated with four of the six National Health Education Standards. Less than half of the educators felt very confident with integrating communication and advocacy skills. The educators surveyed also believed to be very confident in meeting all seven National

Teacher Preparation Standards for Sexuality Education. This article concludes that gauging current teacher’s confidence and proficiency with these standards can isolate factors that either impede or enhance quality sexuality education for youth. Expanding the

understanding of these factors can influence professional development and provide meaning as to what confident and proficient sexuality educators look like in practice.

Relationship between Level of Capability and Level of Confidence of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education

The table below reveals the relationship between the level of capability and level of confidence of private school teachers in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education.

Table 7. Relationship between Level of Capability and Level of Confidence of Private School Teachers in Integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education

Level of Capability	Level of Confidence					Total
	Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Very Low	
Very High	32	3	1	0	0	36
High	3	10	1	1	0	15
Moderate	1	1	2	0	1	5
Low	0	0	0	1	0	1
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	36	14	4	2	1	57

Computed Value (G)= 0.869

P-value= <.001

Decision= Reject Ho

Interpretation= Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the table on the previous page, most of the teachers have very high level of confidence with 36 out of 57 total respondents where 32 have very high, three (3) have high, and one (1) got moderate level of capability in integrating comprehensive sexuality education.

Using the Chi square test of independence at 0.05 level of significance, a computed (χ^2) value of 0.869 was obtained which is above the p-value of <.001. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the level of capability of teachers and their level of confidence in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education. It can be implied that the more capable the teachers are, the more confident they are in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education.

According to the study of Picardal (2022), thematic analysis revealed that teachers have idealistic perceptions of sex education. It is a holistic perspective, it is necessary and beneficial for adolescents, and it requires maturity and mastery of content. Consequently, they experienced drawbacks in integrating the concepts in their repertoire of instruction due to the following reasons. Fearful that curiosity of students leads to sexual activity; inconsistencies in the scope and manner of instructional delivery; and sociocultural elements act as strong oppositions are themes under barriers of sex education integration. Teachers' subject matter knowledge and contexts of teaching might influence their perception and practices.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings of this research study, the conclusions that were arrived at are as follows:

Most of the teacher respondents are females, 30 years old and below, with bachelor's degree and with 10 years and below length of service.

Most of the teacher respondents are teaching science while only 2 respondents are teaching the learning area - personal development.

As a whole, teacher respondents are very highly capable in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE). They can effectively plan, teach, and support students in various CSE topics, including sexuality, reproductive health, gender, relationships, and sexual orientation. They can also collaborate with colleagues and address parental concerns.

As a whole the level of confidence of the teacher respondents in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education is very high. They are very highly confident to deliver the following topics: sexual and reproductive anatomy and physiology, human development and reproduction, changes during puberty and adolescence, sexuality and sexual life cycle, sexual behaviors, pregnancy, prevention of teenage pregnancy, prevention of sexually transmitted infections, prevention of HIV & AIDS, gender identity, gender roles, gender stereotypes, sexual preference, tolerance and respect of individual differences, good touch –bad touch, prevention of gender-based abuse and violence, and media and sexuality.

The expertise of teachers in a particular learning area significantly influenced the level of their capability in integrating CSE.

Regardless of learning areas taught, the level of confidence of teachers do not affect their integration of CSE.

The level of capability and level of confidence of teachers in integrating comprehensive sexuality education go together, as the level of capability increases, likewise their level of confidence increases. The more capable the teachers are, the more confident they are in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education.

With reference to the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

Teachers to be provided trainings and seminars to improve their capability and confidence in integrating Comprehensive Sexuality Education.

Curriculum planners, school administrators and teachers plan and craft strategies on how to integrate sexuality education across subject areas.

Implement comprehensive sexuality education, both in schools and outside of schools through community-based training and outreach.

Encourage the stakeholders to participate and collaborate, for example by reducing resistance and helping to co-create CSE interventions that are compatible with the local and broader context.

There is a need for a comparative analysis of factors shaping the integration of CSE not only in school but as well as in other venues in the community.

Include CSE programs and projects into the School Improvement Plan; initiate and conduct CSE-related classroom activities, research, field studies, and other data collection procedures articulated in the Plan through the school publication/newsletter.

Use the contextualized CSE learning resources; and including CSE in school Learning Action Cells sessions.

Future studies to focus on describing prevalence, explaining relationships, and the generalization of issues affecting the integration of CSE into different educational systems.

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